

**IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS, OHIO
CIVIL DIVISION**

ABSOLUTE RESOLUTIONS INVESTMENTS, LLC 800 Norman Drive, Suite 350 Blooming, MN 55437 PLAINTIFF, v. ERIN ELISE MORAN 669 South St Piqua, OH 45356 DEFENDANT	MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS CASE NUMBER 2023 CV 00333 Judge: Hon. Stacy M. Wall [Transferred from Miami County Municipal Court Case Number 2023 CVF 00897] DEFENDANT'S NOTICE OF FILING EXPERT REPORT (WITH EXPERT REPORT ATTACHED AS EXHIBIT)
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**DEFENDANT'S NOTICE OF FILING EXPERT REPORT
(WITH EXPERT REPORT ATTACHED AS EXHIBIT)**

COMES NOW Defendant, Erin Elise Moran (hereafter, "Moran"), and hereby files Defendant's Notice of Filing Expert Report (hereinafter, "Notice"). The Expert Report of Sam Han, Ph.D. (hereinafter, "Expert Report" or "Report") is attached to this Notice as an Exhibit.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Respectfully submitted on June 10, 2024,

/s/ Andrew Barnes
Andrew Barnes (0098065)
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Attorney for Defendant

**IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS, OHIO
CIVIL DIVISION**

ABSOLUTE RESOLUTIONS INVESTMENTS, LLC 800 Norman Drive, Suite 350 Blooming, MN 55437 PLAINTIFF, v. ERIN ELISE MORAN 669 South St Piqua, OH 45356 DEFENDANT.	MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS CASE NUMBER 2023 CV 00333 Judge: Hon. Stacy M. Wall [Transferred from Miami County Municipal Court Case Number 2023 CVF 00897] CERTIFICATE OF FILING AND SERVICE
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CERTIFICATE OF FILING AND SERVICE

I hereby certify that, on the date set forth below, a true and accurate copy of

**DEFENDANT'S NOTICE OF FILING EXPERT REPORT
(WITH EXPERT REPORT ATTACHED AS EXHIBIT)**

has been filed with this Honorable Court using the Court's Electronic Filing System ("EFS"), which will generate a Notice of Electronic Filing ("NEF") to all counsel of record in this matter, and for which the NEF constitutes service in accordance with Ohio Civ. R. 5.

Respectfully submitted on June 10, 2024,

/s/ Andrew Barnes
Andrew Barnes (0098065)
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90 Rhoades Center Dr
Centerville, Ohio 45458
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Attorney for Defendant

EXHIBIT

IN THE MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS, OHIO
CIVIL DIVISION

<p>ABSOLUTE RESOLUTIONS INVESTMENTS, LLC 800 Norman Drive, Suite 350 Blooming, MN 55437 PLAINTIFF,</p> <p>v.</p> <p>ERIN ELISE MORAN 669 South St Piqua, OH 45356 DEFENDANT.</p>	<p>MIAMI COUNTY COURT OF COMMON PLEAS CASE NUMBER 2023 CV 00333</p> <p>Judge: Hon. Stacy M. Wall</p> <p>[Transferred from Miami County Municipal Court Case Number 2023 CVF 00897]</p> <p>EXPERT REPORT OF SAM HAN, PH.D.</p>
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EXPERT REPORT OF SAM HAN, PH.D.

I, Sam Han, declare as follows:

Background and Foundational Statements

1. I am over the age of eighteen years and am competent to make all of the statements in this Expert Report of Sam Han, Ph.D. (hereafter, "Expert Report" or "Report").
2. I voluntarily give the statements in this Report in support of Defendant Erin Moran (hereafter, "Moran") in the above-captioned proceeding.
3. All statements made herein come from my own personal knowledge unless stated otherwise or clearly apparent by context.
4. Matters of opinion expressed in this Report are my opinions formed based upon my own experience and knowledge.
5. I declare under penalty of perjury under the laws of the United States of America that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, the statements that are contained in this Report are true and correct.
6. I have been retained as an expert witness by Counsel for Moran.

Preliminary Statements Relating to Materials Considered

7. I have been advised that Plaintiff Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC (hereafter, "Absolute") has not identified an expert and no expert report from Absolute has been provided to me.

8. I do not expect to rely on any expert report from Absolute in forming my opinions herein, however, should Absolute provide an expert report that affects my conclusions herein, then intellectual honesty requires me to review Absolute's expert's report to determine whether my conclusions herein are sound in view of newly discovered information.

Experience and General Background Information

9. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), I believe that my most-current curriculum vitae (hereafter, "CV") was attached as an exhibit to Defendant's Disclosure of Expert Under Ohio R. Civ. P. 26(B)(7), which was filed on 2024-MAR-13.

- 10.** I am a member in good standing in the following jurisdictions, bars, or courts:
- a. The Supreme Court of the United States
 - b. The Court of Appeals for the Federal Circuit;
 - c. The Court of Appeals for the Eleventh Circuit;
 - d. The Court of Appeals for the Ninth Circuit
 - e. The Court of Appeals for the Sixth Circuit
 - f. The United States Bankruptcy Appellate Panel for the Tenth Circuit
 - g. The United States District Court for the Northern District of Georgia;
 - h. The State Bar of Georgia;
 - i. The Supreme Court of Georgia;

- j. The Georgia Court of Appeals; and
- k. The United States Patent and Trademark Office.

11. I am a 2001 graduate of Georgia State University School of Law in Atlanta, Georgia.

12. I have a doctorate (Ph.D.) in Biomedical Engineering from Worcester Polytechnic Institute (hereafter, "WPI").

13. I also have a Master's degree in Biomedical Engineering from WPI.

14. During my time at WPI, I worked with graphics and image processors for sophisticated magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and magnetic resonance spectroscopy (MRS) systems.

15. Also, during my time at WPI, I was the systems administrator for several computer networks, including UNIX-based networks with workstations from Sun Microsystems, Hewlett-Packard, Digital Equipment Corporation (DEC) Alpha, and Silicon Graphics systems, among others.

16. I also have a bachelor's degree in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science from the University of Michigan.

17. Given my educational background and experience, I am familiar with the format of various electronically stored documents and meta-data associated with various electronically stored documents, including Microsoft® Excel® spreadsheets.

18. I have practiced law since 2001.

19. My law practice involves multiple areas of the law, including patent law (where I am required to understand the cutting edge of technology for sophisticated clients) and consumer law (where I represent consumers in debt collection lawsuits as well as in Fair Debt

Collection Practices Act lawsuits and counterclaims).

20. I have given professional presentations based on evidence that I have collected from debt-collection cases, which have shown: (a) manufactured documents that appear to be original documents; and (b) printouts that appear to be from original spreadsheets when they are not.

21. I have been involved in numerous consumer law cases, including (but not limited to) the cases that are listed in my CV.

Compensation Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c)

22. My billing rate as an expert witness to evaluate evidence based on electronically stored or electronically transferred documents is \$450 per hour, which I believe to be the normal, customary, and reasonable rate for experts in this area of the law.

23. The reason that \$450/hour is a reasonable and customary rate for reviewing electronically stored files is because the meta data and other hidden information in the electronically stored files are susceptible to corruption and changes unless handled properly, thereby requiring original electronic files to be handled with a certain degree of care or to be saved on an unchangeable medium, such as a compact-disc read-only memory (CDROM).

24. My billing rate as an expert witness to evaluate complex business contracts with multiple sub-parts is \$450 per hour, which I believe to be the normal, customary, and reasonable rate for experts in this area of the law.

25. The reason that \$450/hour is a reasonable and customary rate for reviewing business documents is because such a review requires meticulous attention to detail. The complexity of the documents will become evident from: (a) the list of documents themselves; (b) the other documents referenced within other documents; and (c) the interplay of terms

between various cross-referenced documents.

26. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), I declare that my compensation for this particular case is \$450/hour, which I believe to be a reasonable and customary rate for which I have been retained.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Documents Reviewed

27. In compliance with Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c), I declare that this Report is my complete report, including all of the facts and evidence on which I have relied, along with the methodology that I applied (to the extent that it is not self-evident from the statements herein).

28. I have been retained as an expert to review and form an opinion about whether or not the documents produced by Absolute have been altered, destroyed, concealed, or otherwise modified to impair their value as evidence.

29. It is my understanding that all of the documents that I reviewed were produced by Absolute.

30. The documents produced by Absolute appear to include the following documents:

- a. All pleadings and other papers that have been filed in this case.
- b. "Affidavit of Claim and Certificate of Amount Due," executed by Blake Desmond on 2023-APR-27 (hereafter, "Desmond Affidavit"),¹ which references "normal business records," "computer records," corresponding documents," "records provided to Plaintiff," "compilation of the information provided upon acquisition and information obtained since

¹ The Desmond Affidavit was filed as an Exhibit to the Complaint.

acquisition," unspecified "business records" (referenced multiple times), most (if not all) of which were not attached to the Desmond Affidavit.

- c. "Affidavit of Claim and Certificate of Amount Due," executed by Latasha George-Anderson on 2023-SEP-07 (hereafter, "Anderson Affidavit"),² which references "review of the Bank's books and records," "computerized and hard copy books and records of the Bank," "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets," and unspecified "books and records of the Bank" (referenced multiple times), none of which were attached to the Anderson Affidavit.
- d. "Affidavit of Debt and Ownership of Account," executed by Audrey Fermanich on 2023-OCT-04 (hereafter, "Fermanich Affidavit"),³ which references "normal business records," "computer records," corresponding documents," "records provided to Plaintiff," "business records," "compilation of the information provided upon acquisition and information obtained since acquisition," unspecified "business records" (referenced multiple times), "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets," "813 usb sale 20230224 v1.xlsx" (referenced multiple times), "Notice of Assignment, Sale, or Transfer of Ownership Rights," "Notice of Sale and Assignment of Account," "Agreement," and "Billing Statements for the Account."

² The Anderson Affidavit was filed on 2023-OCT-11 as Exh. A to Plaintiff's Notice of Filing Proof of Claim and Standing (hereafter, "Plaintiff's Notice").

³ The Fermanich Affidavit was filed on 2023-OCT-11 as Exh. B to Plaintiff's Notice of Filing Proof of Claim and Standing (hereafter, "Plaintiff's Notice").

- e. A partially redacted "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets,"⁴ dated 2023-FEB-27 and executed electronically by Laura R. Jensen, Eian Clinkscale, and Lori Talarico, which references an "Asset Schedule" attached as "Exhibit A" and "identified in a file named 831 usb sale 20230224 v1.xlsx[.]"
- f. A ten (10) page printout that bears the title "Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx" (pages numbered from "Page 1 of 10" through "Page 10 of 10," hereafter "1st Spreadsheet Printout").⁵
- g. A one (1) page printout that bears the title "Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_Sale_Contacts_Sup_24FEB2023.xlsx" (page numbered "Page 1 of 1," hereafter "2nd Spreadsheet Printout").⁶
- h. A one (1) page printout that bears the title "Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_Sale_sup_24FEB2023.xlsx" (page numbered "Page 1 of 1," hereafter "3rd Spreadsheet Printout").⁷
- i. A letter dated 2023-FEB-28.

⁴ "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" was filed as Exh. 1 to the Fermanich Affidavit on 2023-OCT-11.

⁵ The 1st Spreadsheet Printout is the first ten (10) pages of Exh. 2 to the Fermanich Affidavit, which was filed on 2023-OCT-11.

⁶ The 2nd Spreadsheet Printout is the eleventh (11th) page of Exh. 2 to the Fermanich Affidavit, which was filed on 2023-OCT-11.

⁷ The 3rd Spreadsheet Printout is the twelfth (12th) page of Exh. 2 to the Fermanich Affidavit, which was filed on 2023-OCT-11.

- j. "Notice of Sale and Assignment of Account," dated 2023-MAR-06.
- k. "Kroger Rewards World Elite Mastercard® Agreement" (pages numbered from "Page 1 of 10" through "Page 10 of 10").
- l. Account Statements from 2019-March through 2023-January.

31. I understand that no other documents were produced and that Absolute has certified in its responses to discovery that no other documents will be produced.

32. I have also reviewed documents from other cases brought by Absolute (excerpts of which are discussed below). Because these excerpts are from lawsuits initiated by Absolute, the original documents should be in the possession, custody, or control of Absolute.

33. In applying the methodology for my expert opinion, I rely on the documents, facts, data, and excerpts of Absolute's own documents that are recited herein (hereafter, "Supporting Materials"), all of which I have been made aware of or personally observed.

34. These Supporting Materials are the kinds of facts or data on which experts in this particular field would reasonably rely in forming an opinion on the subject.

Specific Background Relating to Uncovering Fabricated Documents, Uncovering Proof of Tampering with Evidence, and Uncovering Anomalies with Electronic Documents

35. Based on my education, experience, and training, I have been able to uncover fabricated or manufactured documents in several other cases, uncover tampering with evidence in several other cases, and uncover anomalies with electronic documents.

36. For example, I was the one that uncovered that Asset Acceptance, LLC was using made-for-litigation documents in *Reeves v. Asset Acceptance, LLC*, Case Number 1:13-cv-03413-MHS-RGV (N.D. Ga.) (hereafter, "Reeves Case").

37. Being faced with irrefutable proof that Asset Acceptance, LLC (hereafter,

"Asset") was manufacturing documents that were made to appear as spreadsheets for purposes of litigation, Asset's representative testified under oath as follows:

Q. Would you characterize this as a made for litigation document?

A. Absolutely. That's actually how we -- we call it a Schedule A, but it's for the litigation process.

38. I was also the one that uncovered Asset's made-for-litigation documents in *Asset Acceptance v. Miller*, Case Number 2014-CV-01908 (Montgomery County Court of Common Pleas, Ohio) (hereafter, "Miller Case").

39. Again, when Asset was faced with irrefutable proof of manufacturing documents that were made to appear as spreadsheets for purposes of litigation, Asset's representative testified under oath as follows:

Q. Okay. I was gonna say, would you agree with me that this document is essentially made for litigation?

A. Correct.

40. I was also the one that irrefutably proved that National Collegiate Student Loan Trust 2005-2 (hereafter, "NCSLT") had tampered with evidence and then testified falsely to hide its fabrication of documents in *National Collegiate Student Loan Trust 2005-2 v. Peters*, Case Number 2023-CV-03105 (Montgomery County Court of Common Pleas, Ohio) (hereafter, "Peters Case").

41. My step-by-step explanation and documented proof are demonstrated in the following two (2) filings in the Peters Case: (a) Defendant's Reply Brief on Defendant's Motion for Summary Judgment, filed on 2024-MAR-20; and (b) Defendant's Motion to Sanction

Plaintiff and Plaintiff's Counsel for Fraud Upon the Court, filed on 2024-MAR-20.

42. I have applied the same rigorous methodology and the same rigorous analysis in this case as I did for the Reeves Case, the Miller Case, and the Peters Case.

43. The particular education, training, and experience that is pertinent to my document analysis is my background in electrical engineering and computer science, from which I am able to determine with a reasonable degree of confidence how different document types (e.g., word-processing documents (e.g., ".docx" files), spreadsheets (e.g., ".xlsx" files), portable document format ("PDF") files, etc.) appear in their respective native electronic formats and, further, how those particular documents will appear when printed to paper from their native electronic formats.

44. Additional education, training, and experience as a patent attorney reinforces my knowledge of the different word-processing, spreadsheet, and other document types.

45. With this salient technological background in mind, my methodology in analyzing the documents for potential fraud or fabrication (which is a customary and accepted methodology) includes: (a) inspecting paper copies of the documents produced to determine whether or not there are any inconsistencies that are readily apparent in the printed (paper) form of the document; (b) inspecting any electronic form of the documents (should such electronic documents be available for inspection) from which the paper copies were printed to determine whether or not the printed document is an identical copy of the electronic document; (c) inspecting any underlying meta-data of the electronic documents (should such meta-data be available) to determine whether or not there has been evidence of tampering or other issues that affect the reliability of the electronic documents.

Specific Background Relating to Legal Documents

46. Based on my education, experience, and training, I am qualified to provide expert testimony about what is necessary to show a complete and unbroken chain of title.

47. The methodology that I employ for determining a complete and unbroken chain of title is a customary and accepted methodology employed by others in this field.

48. Specifically, I first determine whether or not the documentation is complete.

49. Thereafter, I determine whether or not the chain of title is unbroken.

50. My methodology for determining whether or not the documentation is complete is by: (a) reviewing each document; (b) determining whether or not the reviewed document cross-references another document (hereafter, "cross-referenced document"); (c) listing every cross-referenced document; (d) determining whether or not the cross-referenced document has been produced (or even exists); (e) if the cross-referenced document has been produced, then repeating (a) through (d) for the cross-referenced document.

51. This step-by-step methodology is repeated until, either: (a) all cross-referenced documents are collected; or (b) missing documents are identified.

52. If there are no missing documents, then the conclusion is that the documentation is complete.

53. If there are missing documents, then the conclusion is that the documentation is not complete.

54. My methodology for determining whether or not the chain of title is unbroken is by tracing forward (from the original owner) every transaction until the last transaction.

55. If there are no gaps from the original owner to the last owner, then the conclusion is that the chain of title is unbroken.

56. If there are gaps from the original owner to the last owner, then the conclusion is

that the chain of title is broken.

57. With all of this background and methodology explained, my opinions (all of which I can state with a reasonable degree of certainty) are as follows.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): First Opinion - The "Asset Schedule" Referenced in the Fermanich Affidavit Cannot Include the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout or the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout Because Neither the 2nd Spreadsheet Nor the 3rd Spreadsheet Are Referenced Anywhere Else or Incorporated by Reference in Any Other Produced Documents

58. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my first opinion is that the "Asset Schedule" that is referenced in the Fermanich Affidavit cannot include either the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout or the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout.

59. Paragraph 8 of the Fermanich Affidavit recites, in relevant part:

20230224 v1.xlsx". Plaintiff produces herewith as Exhibit 2 the entirety of the file named "813 usb sale 20230224 v1.xlsx" which relates to or in any way mentions the Defendant and/or the Account. To protect the personal identifying information and privacy of other consumers whose

60. The attached "Exhibit 2" includes a total of twelve (12) pages.

61. The first ten (10) pages have a heading on each page that recites:

Asset Schedule - Exhibit A
US Bank National Association
2/27/2023
813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx

62. Each of those first ten (10) pages also recite, on the bottom left, a page number:

Page 10 of 10

63. The very first column on each of the first ten (10) pages shows a line number of 1876:

	A	B	C	D
1	Pool Number	Account Number/PAN	Primary Customer Last Name	Primary Customer First Name
1876	813	4418	MORAN	ERIN

64. The eleventh (11th) page has a heading that recites:

Asset Schedule - Exhibit A
 US Bank National Association
 2/27/2023
 813_Sale_Contacts_Sup_24FEB2023.xlsx

65. That eleventh (11th) page also has a page number:

Page 1 of 1

66. The very first column on the 11th page shows a line number of 1023 (which is different from the line number of 1876 that is recited in the first 10 pages):

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	LOT_NUM	REF_ID	ACCT_NUM	FIRST_NAME	MIDDLE_NAME	LAST_NAME
1023	813	1917	4418	ERIN	ELISE	MORAN

67. The twelfth (12th) page has a heading that recites:

Asset Schedule - Exhibit A
 US Bank National Association
 2/27/2023
 813_Sale_sup_24FEB2023.xlsx

68. That twelfth (12th) page also has a page number:

Page 1 of 1

69. The very first column on the 12th page shows a line number of 1004 (which is

different from the line number of 1876 that is recited in the first 10 pages and, also, different from the line number of 1023 that is recited on the 11th page):

	A	B	C
1	LOT_NUM	REF_ID	acct_num
1004	813	1917	4418

70. A side-by-side comparison of the different headings (as shown here) irrefutably demonstrates that these three spreadsheet printouts are not a part of the same file:

Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx	Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_Sale_Contacts_Sup_24FEB2023.xlsx	Asset Schedule - Exhibit A US Bank National Association 2/27/2023 813_Sale_sup_24FEB2023.xlsx
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71. Additionally, the fact that the page numbers clearly show "Page 10 of 10," "Page 1 of 1," and "Page 1 of 1" bolsters the conclusion that these twelve (12) pages are not from the same electronic file.

72. Furthermore, the fact that the line indices are different (e.g., line 1876, line 1023, and line 1004) reinforces the conclusion that these twelve (12) pages are not from the same electronic file.

73. Based on these inconsistencies in the twelve (12) page document, which was labeled as a single "Exhibit 2" and produced in conjunction with the Fermanich Affidavit, I can state with a reasonable degree of certainty (and, indeed, a near-absolute degree of certainty) that "Exhibit 2" of the Fermanich Affidavit cannot be the "Asset Schedule" unless it was modified from select portions of three (3) different files and then concatenated together to form a single 12-page "Exhibit 2" file.

74. Because there is conclusive proof that the "Asset Schedule" is an altered and concatenated document, my first opinion (which I can state with near certainty) is that Exhibit 2 (as a whole) is a manufactured document.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Second Opinion - The 1st Spreadsheet Printout, the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout, and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout Are All Incomplete

75. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my second opinion is that the 1st Spreadsheet Printout (namely, pages 1 through 10 of "Exhibit 2"), the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout (page 11 of "Exhibit 2"), and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout (page 12 of "Exhibit 2") are all incomplete.

76. In addition to having certain portions redacted (which, in itself, is not problematic), the 1st Spreadsheet Printout clearly shows that it includes only line 1876 of an entire compilation.

77. Even presuming that line 1876 is the last line, there are 1875 prior lines that are omitted from the 1st Spreadsheet Printout.

78. Similarly, the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout clearly shows that it includes only line 1023 of another entire compilation.

79. Again, even presuming that line 1023 is the last line, there are 1022 prior lines that are omitted from the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout.

80. Likewise, the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout clearly shows that it includes only line 1004 of yet another entire compilation.

81. Once again, even presuming that line 1004 is the last line, there are 1003 prior lines that are omitted from the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout.

82. Whatever the reason may be for altering documents to include only a single line, what is clear on its face is the fact that the 1st Spreadsheet Printout, the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout, and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout are all incomplete.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Third Opinion - The Original Electronic Version of the 1st Spreadsheet Printout Will Show Numbers That Lack a Decimal Point

83. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my third opinion is that the original electronic version of the 1st Spreadsheet Printout will show numbers that lack a decimal point, which changes a number by two (2) orders of magnitude on a spreadsheet.

84. Although a decimal point (basically, a tiny dot) may not appear to be such a big change when examined on paper, that tiny discrepancy is an enormous difference for computers, especially in programs and spreadsheets where numbers are represented accurately.

85. By comparison, the following excerpts are taken from documents that Absolute produced in other cases:

- a. *Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC v. Timothy McNew*, Case Number CVF 2302559 (Middletown Municipal Court, Butler County, Ohio) (hereafter, "McNew"), showing a charge-off value in both dollars and cents (meaning, with a decimal point (e.g., "5945.55")):

5/22/2023			
	W	X	Y
Term	LoanTermEndDate	SpectrumChargeOffDate	ChargeOffPrinNew
Months	1/3/2024	4/2/2023	5945.55

- b. *Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC v. Carrie Konkle*, Case Number 23CV27277 (Hamilton County Municipal Court, Hamilton County, Ohio) (hereafter, "Konkle"), showing a charge-off value in both dollars and cents (meaning, with a decimal point (e.g., "9,739.92" and "8,592.32")):

RG-2022-137 Fina		
AI	AJ	AK
Charge_Off_Balance_Total	Charge_Off_Balance_Interest	Charge_Off_Balance_Principal
9,739.92	1,147.60	8,592.32

c. *Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC v. Yvonne McKinney*, Case Number 2024CVF00017W (Montgomery County Municipal Court, Montgomery County, Ohio) (hereafter, "McKinney"), showing a charge-off value in both dollars and cents (meaning, with a decimal point (e.g., "9,047.35")):

RG-2022-137 Fina		
AI	AJ	AK
Charge_Off_Balance_Total	Charge_Off_Balance_Interest	Charge_Off_Balance_Principal
9,047.35	1,085.24	7,962.11

86. As shown from Absolute's own documents in McNew, Konkle, and McKinney, a Microsoft® Excel® document is fully capable of storing numbers (especially U.S. currency) in both dollars and cents, thereby including a decimal point.

87. Thus, when a decimal point is missing from a U.S. currency number in Microsoft® Excel®, the absence of that decimal point means one or more of the following: (a) that the decimal point never existed from the outset; (b) that someone actively modified a particular cell in Microsoft® Excel® to remove the decimal point (thereby altering, modifying, or destroying evidence); (c) applied some mathematical operator to that particular cell, which resulted in the removal of the decimal point (again, demonstrating an alteration, a modification, or a destruction); or (d) some combination of (a) through (c).

88. Unlike McNew, Konkle, or McKinney, the Microsoft® Excel® spreadsheet that Absolute produced in this case shows whole numbers, which do not have decimal points (e.g.,

"1121808" and "988709"):

813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx										
	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y
	Primary Customer Preferred Phone Availability Indicator	Primary Customer BusinessOther Phone Number	Primary Customer BusinessOther Phone Type	Primary Customer BusinessOther Phone Do Not Contact Indicator	Primary Customer BusinessOther Phone Availability Indicator	Charge off Date	Original Charge off Total	Current Balance	Total Paid Since Charge off	Original Charge off Principal
	V					1/31/2023	1121808	1121808	0	988709

89. Those numbers (without decimal points), as shown in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout represent an "Original Chargeoff Total" of one-million, one-hundred-and-twenty-one thousand, eight-hundred and eight (1121808) and an "Original Chargeoff Principal" of nine-hundred-eighty-eight thousand, seven-hundred and nine (988709).

90. Based on my education, training, and experience, an examination of the original electronic file (from which this 1st Spreadsheet Printout was printed) will show that the plus-or-minus million number was accurately printed from the electronic Microsoft® Excel® file.

91. In other words, the original electronic version of the 1st Spreadsheet Printout will show the "Original Chargeoff Total" as being "1121808" (without decimal point); not "11218.08" (with decimal point).

92. Similarly, the original electronic version of the 1st Spreadsheet Printout will show the "Original Chargeoff Principal to be "988709" (without decimal point); not "9887.09" (with decimal point).

93. This is significant because, from a computational perspective, the decimal point changes the number by two (2) orders of magnitude.

94. That difference in magnitude creates a discrepancy in documentation, as explained further below.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Fourth Opinion - The Missing Decimal Point Makes the Numbers in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout Irreconcilable with Any of the Numbers in the Fermanich Affidavit

95. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my fourth opinion is that the missing decimal point (as noted above) makes the numbers from the 1st Spreadsheet Printout irreconcilable with any of the numbers that are recited in the Fermanich Affidavit.

96. The Fermanich Affidavit (at ¶ 3) states under oath that "[b]ased upon the business records maintained in regard to the Account," there is a "current balance owing of \$11,218.08" (see Fermanich Affidavit at ¶ 5)

97. That sum of \$11,218.08 (with the decimal point) cannot be reconciled with a number that is exactly one hundred times (100x) larger in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout (namely, "1121808").

98. Again, although this decimal point may seem like a small difference, the removal of that decimal point required deliberate action and a finite amount of time or, alternatively, a computer program that was specifically configured to write (or rewrite) numbers without decimal points.

99. Ultimately, based on my experience, education, background, and my knowledge of how Microsoft® Excel® operates, the "1121808" in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout cannot be reconciled with the 100x smaller number in the Fermanich Affidavit.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Fifth Opinion - The Missing Decimal Point Makes the Numbers in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout Irreconcilable with Any of the Numbers in the Anderson Affidavit

100. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the

Supporting Documents), my fifth opinion is that the missing decimal point makes the numbers from the 1st Spreadsheet Printout irreconcilable with any of the numbers that are recited in the Anderson Affidavit.

101. The Anderson Affidavit (at ¶ 3) states under oath that the "statements made in this Affidavit are based on the computerized and hard copy books and records of the Bank" and that the sum of "\$11,218.08" is based on "the books and records of the Bank" (Anderson Affidavit at ¶ 7).

102. Similar to how the discrepancy in the Fermanich Affidavit cannot be reconciled with the 1st Spreadsheet Printout, the sum of \$11,218.08 (with the decimal point) in the Anderson Affidavit cannot be reconciled with the one-hundred-times (100x) larger number in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout (namely, "1121808").

103. Again, based on my experience, education, background, and my knowledge of how Microsoft® Excel® operates, the "1121808" in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout required deliberate action and a finite amount of time to remove a decimal point or, alternatively, a computer program specifically configured to write (or rewrite) numbers without decimal points.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Sixth Opinion - The Missing Decimal Point Makes the Numbers in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout Irreconcilable with Any of the Numbers in the Desmond Affidavit

104. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my sixth opinion is that the missing decimal point makes the numbers from the 1st Spreadsheet Printout irreconcilable with any of the numbers that are recited in the Desmond Affidavit.

105. Initially, ¶¶ 1 - 7 of the Desmond Affidavit are verbatim identical to ¶¶ 1 - 7 of the Fermanich Affidavit with only two (2) differences: (a) first, Desmond testifies (at ¶ 1) that

he is familiar with the "creation" of the business records, while Fermanich never testifies that she has personal knowledge of how the business records are "created" (which is a significant and substantive difference); and (b) Desmond capitalizes ERIN ELISE MORAN in ¶ 3, while Fermanich capitalizes only the first letters of Erin Elise Moran in ¶ 3 (which is only a difference in form; not in substance). Other than these two (2) differences, ¶¶ 1 - 7 of the Fermanich Affidavit is word-for-word, letter, and punctuation-for-punctuation identical to ¶¶ 1 - 7 of the Desmond Affidavit.

106. The Desmond Affidavit (at ¶ 3) states under oath that "[b]ased upon the business records maintained in regard to the Account," there is a "current balance owing of \$11,218.08" (see Desmond Affidavit at ¶ 5)

107. Once again, that sum of \$11,218.08 (with the decimal point) cannot be reconciled with a number that is exactly one hundred times (100x) larger in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout (namely, "1121808").

108. As noted above, removal of the decimal point required deliberate action and a finite amount of time or, alternatively, a computer program that was specifically configured to write (or rewrite) numbers without decimal points.

109. Ultimately, based on my experience, education, background, and my knowledge of how Microsoft® Excel® operates, the "1121808" in the 1st Spreadsheet Printout cannot be reconciled with the 100x smaller number in the Desmond Affidavit.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Seventh Opinion - The 1st Spreadsheet Printout, the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout, and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout Cannot Represent the Same Transaction Because the Line Indices for Each Are Different

110. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the Supporting Documents), my seventh opinion, which I can state with a reasonable degree of

certainty, is that the 1st Spreadsheet Printout, the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout, and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout cannot represent the same transaction because the line indices for each are different.

111. Specifically, the 1st Spreadsheet Printout lists Moran's alleged account on line 1876; the 2nd Spreadsheet Printout lists Moran's alleged account on line 1023; and the 3rd Spreadsheet Printout lists Moran's alleged account on line 1004.

112. If these three (3) Spreadsheet Printouts listed accounts that were part of the same alleged transfer, then the reference indices for the same account should be the same. However, all three reference indices are different (i.e., line 1876, which is different from line 1023, which is also different from line 1004).

113. The only reasonable explanations for these reference indices being different are, either: (a) the Spreadsheet Printouts do not contain the same number of line entries (in which case the accounts listed in the three different Spreadsheet Printouts cannot be a part of the same transaction); or (b) the entries in the Spreadsheet Printouts are out of sequence (which cannot be reasonably explained).

114. Based on my education, experience, and training (and based on the absence of any explanation of such a discrepancy in the Spreadsheet Printouts), I can say with a reasonable degree of certainty that an examination of the metadata for the original electronic files will likely reveal a last-modified date that cannot be reconciled with the date of any alleged transfer (namely, 2023-FEB-27).

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Eighth Opinion - The Alleged "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" Has Been Altered with the Purpose of Impairing Its Value as Evidence in the Proceedings

115. Based on my experience, education, and training (and also my review of the

Supporting Documents), my eighth opinion is that the alleged "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" has been altered for the purpose of impairing its value as evidence in the proceedings.

116. A substantially identical "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" from U.S. Bank to Absolute can be found in *Absolute Resolutions Investments, LLC v. Tracy E. Deroche*, Case Number 23CVF01244 (Xenia Municipal Court, Green County, Ohio) (hereafter, "DeRoche").

117. Significantly, the DeRoche document clearly shows a page number at the bottom to clearly show that it is only a single page (specifically, p. 34) that is taken from a larger 39-page document, while the corresponding Moran document has the page number conspicuously deleted (as shown in the comparison below):

Exhibit B from DeRoche

Exhibit B from Moran

118. Based on my experience, education, training, and my familiarity with similar documents, this "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" is an exhibit to a larger multi-page document, which is commonly designated in the industry as a "Forward Flow Agreement."

119. By way of example, a 2009-JAN-14 Forward Flow Agreement in which U.S. Bank was defined as the Seller included disclaimers, such as: (a) "THE EXISTENCE OF EVIDENCE OF INDEBTEDNESS SHALL NOT BE DEEMED TO IMPLY THAT THE DEBT EVIDENCED IS ENFORCEABLE" (in bold, all capital letters in the original); (b) "Seller makes no representations or warranties regarding the number of Unenforceable Accounts included in this portfolio"; (c) "On each Transfer Date, for the duration of the Transfer Period, Seller agrees to sell, and Buyer agrees to purchase Assets with an Approximate Unpaid Balance of no less than \$10 million, but no more than \$20 million, subject to the terms, provisions, conditions, limitations, waivers and disclaimers set forth in the Agreement"; (d) "without recourse, warranty or representation, except those expressly made in this Agreement"; (e) "all requests for Evidence of Indebtedness shall be provided to Seller on an encrypted spreadsheet using such encryption software as approved by Seller"; (f) "Buyer acknowledges that its failure to comply with the provisions of this Section may affect Buyer's rights in any such litigation or other legal proceeding including, without limitation, any dismissal with prejudice or the running of any statute of limitations if any such action or other legal proceeding is dismissed"; (g) "Buyer acknowledges and agrees that the Assets may be Unenforceable Accounts and may have little or no value" (in bold, underlined text in original); (h) "THE ASSETS ARE BEING SOLD 'AS IS' AND 'WITH ALL FAULTS', WITHOUT ANY REPRESENTATION OR WARRANTY WHATSOEVER, AND SELLER SPECIFICALLY

DISCLAIMS ANY WARRANTY, GUARANTY OR REPRESENTATION, ORAL OR WRITTEN, PAST OR PRESENT, EXPRESS OR IMPLIED, CONCERNING THE ASSETS, THE STRATIFICATION OR PACKAGING OF THE ASSETS" (in all capital letters with certain sections in bold, underlined text); and (i) Buyer acknowledges that the Assets may be Unenforceable Account."

120. If the terms and conditions of the Forward Flow Agreement in this case have corresponding provisions as those set forth above, then those corresponding provisions would be relevant and applicable to whether Absolute can even bring this case.

121. It is my understanding that Absolute has admitted that it has possession of the Forward Flow Agreement but has refused to produce that Forward Flow Agreement.

122. Based on my familiarity with document formats (such as Microsoft® Word® and Adobe® PDF files), I can state with a reasonable degree of certainty that page numbers do not inexplicably vanish from the bottom margin of a document.

123. To remove the page number from a Microsoft® Word® document, one must deliberately select the text in the margin and delete that selected text (it is normally a four-step process of entering the margin, selecting the text in the margin, deleting that selected text, and then exiting the margin).

124. Removing the page number from an Adobe® PDF document is a more deliberate task than what is required in Microsoft® Word, namely, either: (a) purchasing an Adobe® editor and removing the text; or (b) masking the text by overlaying a white box over the text to hide it.

125. For these "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" documents, removing the page number from the bottom of the page impairs the document's value as

evidence.

126. This is because removing (or hiding) that page number would prevent the least sophisticated consumer from ever knowing that the "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" was only a single page from a multi-page document.

127. Ultimately, it is my expert opinion that: (a) the original version of "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" for this case had a page number (just as it is shown in the DeRoche document); (b) "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" in this case has been altered or otherwise modified; and (c) that alteration or modification was deliberate and intentional.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Ninth Opinion - The Desmond Affidavit Is a Robo-Signed Document That Was Executed without Reviewing the Documents Referenced Therein

128. Based on my experience, education, and training, I can state with a reasonable degree of certainty that the Desmond Affidavit was "robo-signed" without Desmond reviewing all of the documents referenced therein.

129. Had Desmond reviewed all of the documents that are referenced in the Desmond Affidavit, then Desmond would have caught the same discrepancies in those documents that I caught when reviewing them.

130. For example, Desmond would have noticed at least the following discrepancies: (a) the different .xlsx filenames; (b) the disjunctive page numbers (going from "Page 10 of 10" to "Page 1 of 1" to "Page 1 of 1" (a second time)); (c) the incongruous line indices; (d) the missing decimal point; and (e) the missing page number at the bottom of "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets."

131. Additionally, if Desmond had reviewed all of the documents, then it is unclear

why another affidavit (namely, the Fermanich Affidavit) with verbatim identical language was needed.

132. In my expert opinion, robo-signing an affidavit without reviewing the documents referenced therein is deceptive.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Tenth Opinion - The Anderson Affidavit Was Executed without Reviewing the Documents Referenced Therein

133. Based on my experience, education, and training, I can state with a reasonable degree of certainty that the Anderson Affidavit was also "robo-signed" without Anderson reviewing all of the documents referenced therein.

134. Similar to the discrepancies missed by Desmond, if Anderson had actually reviewed the referenced documents, then Anderson would have noticed: (a) the different .xlsx filenames; (b) the disjunctive page numbers (going from "Page 10 of 10" to "Page 1 of 1" to "Page 1 of 1" (a second time); (c) the incongruous line indices; (d) the missing decimal point; and (e) the missing page number at the bottom of "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets."

135. Additionally, what is conspicuously missing from the Anderson Affidavit is any affirmation that Anderson's statements are based on personal knowledge.

136. Moreover, the bottom margin of the Anderson Affidavit shows, on its face, that it is a form document from "5.29.18"

Affidavit (USB sold) 5.29.18 approved

137. The phrases that are underlined in the form affidavit appear to be "fill-in-the-blank" sections, which Anderson seems to have completed before executing the form.

138. Consequently, it is not surprising that: (a) none of the documents, books, records, electronic files, or any other referenced document were attached or produced in conjunction with the Anderson Affidavit; and (b) Anderson also failed to notice all of the discrepancies in the alleged U.S. Bank documents.

139. Ultimately, based on my experience, education, and training, it is my expert opinion that the Anderson Affidavit was robo-signed, not based on personal knowledge, and without a proper review of the documents that were expressly referenced in the Anderson Affidavit.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Eleventh Opinion - Fermanich's Consistent Error in Replacing the Number "1" with the Lowercase Letter "L" in the File Names Demonstrates That Fermanich Neither Has Personal Knowledge of the Actual File nor a Knowledge of How the Electronic Files Are Created

140. Although the difference between a lowercase "L" and a number "1" may appear trivial, this difference demonstrates that Fermanich either did not write her own affidavit or, alternatively, did not have personal knowledge of Absolute's computer records and files.

141. Repeatedly, Fermanich references the following file (with direct quotation marks):

"813 usb sale 20230224 vl.xlsx"

142. Close scrutinization reveals that the ".xlsx" filename (which is a Microsoft® Excel® file extension) is version "L" (the alphabetic letter); not version "1" (the number).

143. The font itself is remarkably different between an "L" and a "1," as highlighted here:

“813 usb sale 20230224 v1.xlsx”

144. The number "1" has a top serif and a foot serif, while the lowercase letter "L" is a straight vertical line without any serif (meaning, no whip or tail on the lowercase letter "L").

145. The 1st Spreadsheet Printout shows "v1" (version-one) not "vl" (version-L), as follows:

813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx
813_usb_sale_20230224_v1.xlsx

146. The allegedly case-dispositive and central document, the "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets," references version-one ("v1"), as shown here (note that the number "1" is shorter in length than the lowercase letter "L"):

813 usb sale 20230224 v1.xlsx

147. On a computer keyboard, the letter "L" is located on the far-right side and normally typed with the ring finger of the right hand, while the number "1" is located on the far-left side (at the top) and normally typed with the pinky finger of the left hand.

148. The two (2) keys could not be farther apart in location, function, meaning, and how they are typed.

149. In other words, it is virtually impossible to mistakenly type the letter "L" for the number "1."

150. The Fermanich Affidavit types the letter "L" at least five (5) times.

151. Based on my experience, education, and training, it is my expert opinion that the

version-L ("v1") that was typed five (5) times in the Fermanich Affidavit was an intentional and deliberate recitation of the letter (not the number).

152. What this leads me to conclude is that: (a) Fermanich does not have personal knowledge of how the files are created and stored (which means that she cannot authenticate the 1st Spreadsheet Printout); or (b) Fermanich did not review the Fermanich Affidavit (which means that her affirmation under penalty of perjury is a false affidavit); or (c) someone other than Fermanich wrote the Fermanich Affidavit (which means that only the author can explain why the letter "L" is typed in place of the number "1").

153. No matter the explanation, it is clear that the Fermanich Affidavit does not authenticate either the "Exhibit B Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets" or the Asset Schedule (referenced herein as the 1st Spreadsheet Printout).

154. Again, even though the difference may appear trivial, what cannot reasonably be disputed is that someone deliberately and intentionally (and not by mistake) typed the letter "L" and authenticated the wrongly named document.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Twelfth Opinion - The Chain of Title Is Incomplete Because Documents and Records That Are Referenced in the Anderson Affidavit Are Missing

155. The Anderson Affidavit references "the Bank's books and records," "computerized and hard copy books and records of the Bank," "Bill of Sale and Assignment of Assets," and unspecified "books and records of the Bank" (referenced multiple times).

156. However, none of these referenced documents were attached to the Anderson Affidavit.

157. Thus, based on my education, training, and experience, I conclude with a reasonable degree of certainty that the chain of title is incomplete.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Thirteenth Opinion - The Chain of Title Is Incomplete Because Documents and Records That Are Referenced in the Desmond Affidavit Are Missing

158. The Desmond Affidavit references "normal business records," "computer records," "corresponding documents," "records provided to Plaintiff," "compilation of the information provided upon acquisition and information obtained since acquisition," and unspecified "business records" (referenced multiple times).

159. However, none of these referenced documents were attached to the Desmond Affidavit.

160. Thus, based on my education, training, and experience, I conclude with a reasonable degree of certainty that the chain of title is incomplete.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Fourteenth Opinion - The Chain of Title Is Incomplete Because the Business Records on Which Desmond Relied Are a "Compilation," But the Documents That Were Used to Manufacture the Compilation Were Neither Identified Completely nor Produced

161. The Desmond Affidavit, in ¶ 3, states that the business records are a "compilation."

162. By definition, a compilation is something that has been gathered together from other sources.⁸

163. None of those other sources have ever been identified with particularity or provided for review in conjunction with the Desmond Affidavit.

164. Without those underlying documents, I conclude with a reasonable degree of

⁸ Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines "compiled" to mean "gathered together especially from various sources."

certainty that the chain of title is incomplete.

Substance of Report Under Ohio Civ. R. 26(B)(7)(c): Fifteenth Opinion - The Chain of Title Is Incomplete Because the Business Records on Which Fermanich Relied Are a "Compilation," But the Documents That Were Used to Manufacture the Compilation Were Neither Identified Completely nor Produced

165. The Fermanich Affidavit, in ¶ 3, states that the business records are a "compilation."

166. Once again, by definition, a compilation is something that is gathered from other sources.

167. And, once again, none of those other sources have ever been identified with particularity or provided for review in conjunction with the Fermanich Affidavit.

168. Without those underlying documents, I conclude with a reasonable degree of certainty that the chain of title is incomplete.

Concluding Remarks

169. Ultimately, it is clear that several documents were either fabricated or subjected to tampering (or both).

170. If original, unmodified electronic documents are provided for review, then I can provide a more accurate assessment of how, precisely, the documents were created, stored, transferred, or otherwise manipulated over time.

171. Additionally, even with the documents that have been provided (which I understand to be the complete set of documents on which Absolute relies), there are inconsistencies that cannot be reasonably explained based on how computers work.

172. It is my opinion (based on my education, training, and experience) that the

statements by Absolute that it owns an alleged debt is based on fabricated documents, modified documents, and missing documents, all of which constitute false and misleading statements.

173. I reserve the right to amend any statements herein, should new information become available (such as a late-filed expert report by Absolute , or late-produced documents that Absolute previously alleged to be irrelevant that Absolute must now produce to overcome the facts recited herein).

FURTHER DECLARANT SAYETH NAUGHT.

[SIGNATURE TO FOLLOW]

Executed on 2024-June-04, in Dayton, Ohio.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Sam Han", written over a solid black horizontal line.

Sam Han
Expert for Erin Moran